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NEWS

Visual Astronomy Display: August 2014

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Visual Astronomy Display for August 2014

Highlights...

- The tale of the comet-chasing probe, **Rosetta**, re-imagined as a child's bedtime story;
- Last month was the **45th anniversary of the moon landing!** Several videos in this playlist celebrate and remember that historic event;
- SciShow has a video highlighting **rogue planets**, those lone rocky bodies that float through space without a star to call their own;
- The upcoming **Perseid Meteor shower coincides with a "supermoon"** this year! Science@NASA has a video describing the effects of this unique event; and
- NASA is gearing up the New Horizon's mission with is only one year away from its **destination: Pluto!** Starting in April 2015, the satellite will be close enough to this distant world to take photos rivaling those taken by the Hubble Space Telescope.

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Bonus Videos...

- In honor of the 45th anniversary of the Apollo 11 moon landing, NASA held a panel titled “[NASA's Next Giant Leap](#)” at San Diego Comic-Con International 2014. Hosted by Seth Green, panelists were Dr. Jim Green (NASA's division director of Planetary Science), Buzz Aldrin (Apollo 11 Astronaut), Mike Fincke (NASA Astronaut), and Bobak “Mohawk Guy” Ferdowsi (NASA-JPL Engineer; Curiosity and Europa Missions). Recorded July 28, 2014.
- Also in honor of the 45th anniversary of the Apollo 11 moon landing, NASA has [gathered audio highlights from all nine days of the Apollo 11 mission](#). The [audio from day 5](#) contains two of the [most famous](#) phrases ever spoken in space.

[Playlist Archive](#) [Suggestions](#), [Comments](#), or [Questions](#)

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Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

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